

The Impact of Ghana's Electronic Transfer Levy (E-Levy) on Mobile Money Adoption and Financial Inclusion: A Natural Policy Experiment (2018-2025)

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Data Availability Statement

Data and code for this study will be made upon request.

Abstract

The rapid expansion of mobile money has significantly improved financial inclusion across Sub-Saharan Africa. In Ghana, the introduction of the Electronic Transfer Levy (E-Levy) in May 2022 raised concerns about its impact on digital financial services. This study examines the effects of the E-Levy on mobile money activity and financial inclusion using monthly data from September 2018 to December 2025. Employing an Interrupted Time Series framework with HAC (Newey-West) robust standard errors, the analysis evaluates the levy introduction, the January 2023 rate reduction, and the April 2025 repeal on transaction value, volume, active accounts, active agents, and substitution toward GH-Link. Results show that the E-Levy significantly reduced mobile money transaction activity. A one percentage point increase in the levy rate is associated with a level-shift coefficient of -0.250 ($p < 0.001$) for transaction value ($\approx 22\%$ reduction) and -0.071 ($p < 0.01$) for transaction volume ($\approx 7\%$ reduction). While active accounts remained relatively stable, their growth and agent network expansion slowed. Significant substitution toward the untaxed GH-Link platform was also observed. Following the April 2025 repeal, the repeal dummy was statistically insignificant ($p = 0.587$), indicating short-run behavioral persistence. The findings suggest that digital transaction taxes can generate unintended consequences for financial inclusion by reducing transaction intensity and encouraging platform substitution. They highlight the need to carefully balance revenue mobilization with digital transformation goals in developing economies.

Keywords: Mobile Money, Financial Inclusion, E-Levy, Digital Taxation, Interrupted Time Series, Ghana

Introduction

Mobile money has been one of the most transformative innovations for financial inclusion in Sub-Saharan Africa. In Ghana, mobile money has grown rapidly since its introduction, serving as a critical tool for the unbanked and underbanked population. By facilitating person-to-person⁷⁷⁸ transfers, merchant payments, and access to basic financial services, mobile money has significantly expanded financial access, especially among women, rural residents, and low-income households.

In May 2022, the Government of Ghana introduced the Electronic Transfer Levy (E-Levy), a 1.5% tax on most electronic transactions above a daily threshold. The primary objectives were to broaden the tax base, increase domestic revenue mobilisation, and promote formalisation of the economy. However, the policy sparked widespread public debate and protests, with critics arguing that it would undermine progress in digital financial inclusion by increasing the cost of using mobile money platforms. In January 2023, the rate was reduced to 1% following public pressure, and the levy was eventually repealed on 2 April 2025. This policy sequence — introduction, rate reduction, and full repeal — provides a rare natural experiment to study the full lifecycle of a digital transaction tax.

This study examines the effects of the E-Levy on mobile money adoption and broader financial inclusion in Ghana using high-frequency monthly data from September 2018 to December 2025 (88 observations). The period covers more than three years before the policy, the period of the levy at two different rates, and the post-repeal period. This allows analysis of both short-term disruptions and medium- to long-term adjustments.

Despite the importance of the topic, existing studies have largely focused on the short-term impact (2022–early 2023) using either survey data or limited transaction aggregates. This

paper contributes to the literature by providing one of the most comprehensive assessments to date using official Bank of Ghana monthly data. It analyses not only transaction volumes and values but also active accounts, active agents, substitution to other digital payment platforms, and differential recovery after the rate cut and repeal.

The findings are highly policy-relevant for Ghana and other developing countries considering taxes on digital financial transactions. Understanding whether such levies create lasting damage to financial inclusion or merely temporary adjustments is critical for designing future digital economy policies. Importantly, the April 2025 repeal allows examination of recovery dynamics, although the short post-repeal window (nine months) limits conclusions about longer-term reversal.

Research Objectives

General Objective: To examine the impact of Ghana's Electronic Transfer Levy (E-Levy) on mobile money adoption and financial inclusion over the period 2018-2025.

Specific Objectives:

1. To assess the short-term and medium-term effects of the E-Levy on mobile money transaction value and volume.
2. To evaluate the impact of the E-Levy on the growth of active mobile money accounts and active agents.
3. To analyse substitution effects between mobile money and other digital payment channels such as GH-Link.
4. To examine the heterogeneous effects of the E-Levy on different demographic groups using Global Findex data through descriptive analysis and discussion.

5. To determine the extent to which any adverse effects persisted or reversed after the rate reduction in January 2023 and after the full repeal in April 2025.

Research Questions

1. To what extent did the introduction of the E-Levy affect mobile money transaction values and volumes in the short term and medium term?

2. How did the E-Levy influence the number of active mobile money accounts and active agents?

3. Did users and businesses substitute mobile money transactions with alternative digital payment methods such as GH-Link following the levy?

4. Were the impacts more pronounced among vulnerable groups such as women, rural dwellers, and low-income populations?

5. What lessons can be drawn from the post-2022 recovery patterns and the eventual repeal of the E-Levy regarding taxation of digital financial services?

Hypotheses

- **H1:** The introduction of the E-Levy had a statistically significant negative immediate effect on mobile money transaction value and volume.

- **H2:** The E-Levy slowed the growth rate of active mobile money accounts and active agents.

- **H3:** There was significant substitution from mobile money to other electronic payment platforms such as GH-Link after the introduction of the E-Levy.

- **H4:** The negative effects were more pronounced among women, rural residents, and the poorest population segments.

- **H5:** The adverse effects diminished over time, with evidence of recovery after the rate reduction in January 2023 and after the full repeal in April 2025.

Literature Review

Mobile Money and Financial Inclusion in Africa

Mobile money has become one of the most transformative financial innovations in sub-Saharan Africa over the past two decades. The rapid expansion of mobile phone penetration, combined with weak traditional banking infrastructure, created opportunities for digital financial services to expand financial access among previously excluded populations. Early literature established that mobile money reduces transaction costs, improves information flows, and strengthens financial participation among low-income households. Aker and Mbiti (2010) argued that mobile technologies reduced market inefficiencies and enhanced economic participation in developing countries. Similarly, Aron (2018) showed that mobile money contributes to financial deepening, consumption smoothing, and informal insurance mechanisms within African economies.

A major contribution to the literature came from the work of Jack and Suri (2014) and Suri and Jack (2016) on Kenya's M-Pesa system. Their studies demonstrated that mobile money significantly improved household welfare, reduced poverty, and enhanced financial resilience, especially among women and rural households. The findings suggested that mobile money functions not merely as a payment technology but also as an important mechanism for economic inclusion and poverty reduction.

Evans and Pirchio (2015) found that successful mobile money systems depend heavily on interoperability, agent density, and network effects. Their study showed that mobile money adoption accelerates once a critical threshold of users and agents is reached. This finding is particularly relevant for Ghana, where interoperability reforms and rapid agent expansion after 2018 contributed significantly to the growth of mobile money usage.

The broader financial inclusion literature further supports the developmental importance of digital finance. Evidence from the Global Findex database shows that account ownership increased substantially in developing economies between 2011 and 2021, with mobile money playing a central role in sub-Saharan Africa (Demirguç-Kunt et al., 2022). Persistent inequalities nevertheless remain across gender, income, and rural-urban groups.

Recent evidence by the World Bank in the Global Findex Database 2024 further confirms that digital financial services remain strongly associated with mobile phone ownership, internet access, and affordability of digital transactions. The report argues that transaction costs remain one of the most important barriers to sustained digital financial usage among poorer households and rural populations (World Bank, 2025). This is directly relevant to the Ghanaian E-Levy debate because increases in transaction costs may discourage low-income users from fully participating in the digital financial ecosystem.

Additional evidence from sub-Saharan Africa suggests that social networks and trust structures play an important moderating role in mobile money adoption. A study by Bongomin et al. (2017) on mobile money and financial inclusion in sub-Saharan Africa found that stronger social networks increase the effectiveness of mobile money adoption and financial participation, particularly among financially excluded populations. This suggests that policy shocks that reduce trust or convenience may weaken digital financial participation among vulnerable users.

Recent regional evidence further highlights the persistent disparities in digital financial access. Jallow and Tajmouati (2025) found that despite overall improvements in headline indicators, factors such as gender, income level, and rural residence remain significant barriers to digital inclusion across West and Central Africa. While Ghana leads the region in mobile money account ownership, the disproportionate exclusion of women and low-income groups suggests

that regressive measures, such as transaction-based taxes, may exacerbate existing inequalities by placing a heavier burden on those already marginalized within the digital ecosystem.

Mobile Money and Financial Inclusion in Ghana

Ghana has emerged as one of Africa's leading mobile money economies. Since the introduction of mobile money services in 2009, the country has experienced rapid growth in transaction values, transaction volumes, active accounts, and agent networks. According to the Bank of Ghana's official payment systems data, mobile money transactions expanded dramatically from 2015 onward. This growth was initially driven by interoperability reforms and agent network expansion, and later reinforced by policy adaptations, enhanced regulatory frameworks, and deeper integration into Ghana's digital ecosystem (Bank of Ghana, 2026).

The introduction of interoperability systems by the Ghana Interbank Payment and Settlement Systems significantly improved digital payment efficiency in Ghana. Interoperability allowed seamless transfers across mobile networks and bank accounts, thereby reducing transaction friction and increasing trust in digital payment systems.

The COVID-19 pandemic further accelerated digital payment adoption in Ghana as households and businesses increasingly relied on contactless transactions. Mobile money became essential for person-to-person transfers, merchant payments, remittances, and savings mobilisation during the pandemic period.

Recent evidence from rural Ghana demonstrates that digital financial services have broader developmental implications beyond payments alone. A study by Atta-Ankomah et al. (2024) on digital financial services and livelihood diversification in rural Ghana found that access to digital financial services improved household income diversification, resilience, and non-farm economic participation. The study showed that mobile money usage helped rural

households manage risks and expand economic opportunities. These findings suggest that policies that reduce digital transaction activity may have wider socioeconomic consequences beyond the financial sector itself.

However, despite these gains, concerns emerged regarding the sustainability of digital financial inclusion after the introduction of the Electronic Transfer Levy (E-Levy) in 2022. Critics argued that taxing electronic transactions could discourage digital payments, reduce financial inclusion, and increase reliance on cash transactions.

Taxation of Digital Financial Services

The taxation of digital financial services has become an increasingly important issue in developing economies seeking to broaden domestic revenue mobilisation. Governments have increasingly viewed digital transactions as a potential tax base because of their rapid growth and traceability. Proponents of digital transaction taxes argue that such taxes improve fiscal sustainability and promote formalisation of economic activity. However, critics contend that taxing digital payments may undermine financial inclusion by increasing transaction costs for low-income users.

Empirical evidence from African countries generally suggests that mobile money taxes reduce transaction activity. Studies from Uganda found that taxes on mobile money withdrawals and transfers caused substantial declines in usage shortly after implementation. Katusiime (2021) showed that macroeconomic policies and regulatory interventions negatively affected mobile money usage in Uganda, particularly among poorer users who were highly sensitive to transaction costs.

Studies from Kenya similarly reported that increases in transaction fees and excise duties reduced mobile money usage intensity. Diouf et al. (2023) found that higher taxation on mobile

money transactions negatively affected financial inclusion outcomes, especially among low-income users. Evidence showed that users often responded by reducing transaction sizes, increasing cash usage, or switching to alternative payment channels. These findings are consistent with transaction cost theory, which predicts that increases in marginal transaction costs discourage usage among low-income consumers.

Recent African evidence further strengthens this argument. Ren et al. (2025) found that while governments may generate immediate fiscal gains from digital transaction taxes, excessive taxation risks stifling long-term digital financial participation and undermining broader financial inclusion objectives. Their study emphasizes a critical trade-off: policymakers must strike a delicate balance between aggressive revenue mobilization and the sustainability of digital financial ecosystems in developing economies.

The literature also highlights substitution effects as an important behavioural response to digital taxes. When one payment channel becomes relatively expensive, users may shift toward untaxed or lower-cost alternatives. Such substitution weakens the effectiveness of transaction taxes because part of the expected tax revenue may be offset by behavioural adjustments and migration toward alternative payment systems.

Recent studies further emphasise the trade-off between revenue mobilisation and financial inclusion. Mpofo (2022) argued that while digital taxes may provide short-term fiscal gains, they can simultaneously undermine long-term financial inclusion and digitalisation objectives in developing economies. This tension has become central in policy debates surrounding digital financial taxation in Africa.

The Ghana E-Levy and Existing Empirical Evidence

The introduction of Ghana's Electronic Transfer Levy (E-Levy) in May 2022 generated significant public, political, and academic debate. The levy initially imposed a 1.5% tax on most electronic transactions above a daily threshold before being reduced to 1% in January 2023 and eventually repealed in April 2025. This policy sequence created a rare natural experiment for evaluating the effects of digital transaction taxation.

Existing empirical studies consistently report negative short-term effects on mobile money activity. Takyi (2025) examined the short-run impact of the E-Levy using monthly time-series data from January 2019 to February 2023. The study found that the levy reduced the value of mobile money transactions by approximately 47%, transaction volumes by 24%, and interoperability transaction values by 49%. However, the study also suggested that the negative effects diminished gradually over time.

More recent studies expanded the analysis beyond aggregate transaction data. Turkson et al. (2025) examined the effect of the E-Levy on retail digital financial services using survey data from urban micro-enterprises across Ghana. The study found substantial declines in mobile money usage, turnover, and customer activity following the levy's implementation, with the strongest effects observed among female-owned businesses and smaller enterprises.

Other studies focused on customer behaviour and perceptions. Anabila et al. (2024) investigated how the E-Levy affected customer satisfaction and perceived value of mobile money services in Ghana. Using structural equation modelling, the study found that the E-Levy negatively moderated customer satisfaction and reduced the perceived value associated with mobile money innovation.

The public opposition to the E-Levy was also substantial. An Afrobarometer survey reported that a majority of Ghanaians opposed the E-Levy and lacked confidence that the tax revenues would be effectively used for national development programmes (Afrobarometer, 2022). The survey further revealed that opposition was strongest among lower-income respondents and digitally active populations. This public resistance likely contributed to behavioural adjustments in transaction patterns and avoidance strategies.

Industry evidence from the GSMA similarly warned that the E-Levy could negatively affect financial inclusion and Ghana's digital economy. GSMA (2022) argued that taxes on mobile money transactions disproportionately burden low-income users because such users typically conduct frequent low-value transactions. The report further suggested that the levy risked slowing digital transformation and weakening trust in digital financial systems.

Despite these contributions, important gaps remain within the literature. First, most studies focus primarily on the short-run implementation period between 2022 and early 2023. Second, many rely on surveys or forecasting approaches rather than long-horizon Interrupted Time Series analysis using official monthly data. Third, existing studies rarely examine the full policy lifecycle, including the rate reduction in 2023 and the repeal in 2025. Finally, limited attention has been paid to substitution toward alternative payment channels such as GH-Link and interoperability systems.

Behavioural Responses and Financial Inclusion Implications

Economic theory suggests that users respond to transaction taxes through behavioural adaptation rather than complete market exit. Instead of abandoning digital platforms entirely, users may reduce transaction frequency, lower transaction sizes, split transactions to remain below taxable thresholds, or migrate toward alternative payment channels.

Existing literature supports these predictions. Studies from Uganda and Kenya found that digital transaction taxes primarily reduced usage intensity rather than account ownership (Diouf et al., 2023; Katusiime, 2021). This distinction is important because financial inclusion measured only by account ownership may overstate actual financial participation if users actively reduce transaction activity due to higher costs.

Behavioural persistence also appears important. Once users adopt alternative payment behaviours, transaction patterns may not immediately revert even after taxes are reduced or removed. This phenomenon, often described as hysteresis, implies that temporary policy shocks may generate long-lasting behavioural effects.

The Ghanaian evidence increasingly supports this interpretation. Tetteh et al. (2023) found that many users adjusted transaction behaviour to minimise tax exposure rather than abandoning digital finance completely. Evidence of increased usage of alternative channels such as bank transfers and interoperability platforms further suggest substitution effects within Ghana's broader digital payment ecosystem.

Empirical Literature and Methodological Approaches

Previous studies examining mobile money taxation have employed several empirical approaches, including descriptive analysis, forecasting models, survey methods, panel regression, autoregressive distributed lag (ARDL) models, and quasi-experimental techniques. While these approaches provide important insights, they also face limitations regarding causal identification and long-term policy evaluation.

Survey-based studies are useful for understanding perceptions and behavioural responses but may suffer from recall bias, limited sample sizes, and short observation windows.

Forecasting and counterfactual approaches similarly provide useful estimates but may not fully capture long-term structural adjustments.

Interrupted Time Series (ITS) analysis has increasingly become an important quasi-experimental method for evaluating policy interventions with clearly defined implementation dates. Wagner et al. (2002), Bernal et al. (2017), and Linden (2015) demonstrated that ITS models are well suited for evaluating policy shocks when randomised experiments are not feasible.

ITS models estimate both immediate level changes and post-intervention trend changes while controlling for underlying trends and seasonality. This makes the approach particularly appropriate for analysing Ghana's E-Levy because the policy involved clearly identifiable intervention points: introduction in May 2022, rate reduction in January 2023, and repeal in April 2025.

The use of Newey and West (1987) HAC standard errors further strengthens time-series estimation by correcting for autocorrelation and heteroskedasticity commonly present in monthly macroeconomic data. Residual stationarity testing using Augmented Dickey-Fuller procedures (Dickey & Fuller, 1979) also helps ensure that estimated relationships are not spurious.

Research Gap

Although the literature on digital financial taxation has expanded rapidly in recent years, several important gaps remain. First, most existing studies on Ghana's E-Levy focus only on the immediate post-implementation period and therefore do not capture medium-term behavioural adjustments, the 2023 rate reduction, or the 2025 repeal.

Second, many studies rely primarily on survey evidence, descriptive statistics, or forecasting approaches rather than high-frequency official monthly transaction data spanning the

full policy cycle. Third, limited research examines substitution effects toward alternative digital payment systems such as GH-Link and interoperability channels. Fourth, few studies distinguish clearly between financial inclusion as account ownership and financial inclusion as transaction usage intensity.

Furthermore, although several studies discuss the regressive implications of digital transaction taxes, limited research combines supply-side transaction data with demand-side financial inclusion indicators such as the Global Findex database. Existing literature therefore provides limited insight into how digital taxes may affect vulnerable demographic groups within broader financial inclusion frameworks.

This study contributes to the literature in several important ways. First, it provides a comprehensive analysis of Ghana's E-Levy covering the full policy lifecycle from introduction to repeal using official monthly data from 2018 to 2025. Second, it employs Interrupted Time Series analysis to estimate immediate effects, post-policy trends, and repeal dynamics while controlling for macroeconomic conditions and seasonality. Third, the study explicitly examines substitution toward alternative digital payment channels such as GH-Link. Finally, it integrates Global Findex evidence to contextualise the financial inclusion implications of digital transaction taxation in Ghana.

Data and Methodology

Data Sources

This study employs high-frequency monthly time series data from the Bank of Ghana and Ghana Statistical Service covering the period September 2018 to December 2025. However, because the macroeconomic controls enter in first-differenced form, the effective estimation sample for all regressions is 87 observations (October 2018 – December 2025). The raw data provide a robust pre-intervention trend of more than three years. Key variables include:

- Mobile money transaction value (Tot_val_trans_mm)
- Mobile money transaction volume (Tot_vol_trans_mm)
- Active mobile money accounts (Active_momo)
- Active agents (Active_Agents)
- GH-Link transaction value (Tot_Trans_Val_ghlink) for substitution analysis
- Macroeconomic controls: inflation, exchange rate growth, the Composite Index of Economic Activity (CIEA), and remittances
- Month dummies (February omitted) for seasonality

Remittance data are reported quarterly by the Bank of Ghana. To obtain a monthly series consistent with the frequency of other variables, quarterly totals were divided equally by three and assigned to each month within the quarter.

All models use the maximum available consistent sample. The Global Findex database (2011, 2014, 2017, 2021, 2024 waves) is used descriptively for heterogeneity discussion (H4).

Econometric Strategy

This study employs an Interrupted Time Series (ITS) framework to estimate the impact of Ghana's Electronic Transfer Levy (E-Levy) on mobile money adoption and financial inclusion outcomes. ITS is appropriate because the policy intervention occurred at clearly identifiable points in time: the introduction of the levy in May 2022, the reduction of the levy rate in January 2023, and the repeal of the levy in April 2025.

The primary level specification is estimated as:

$$Y_t = \beta_0 + \beta_1 Trend_t + \beta_2 LevyRate_t + \beta_3 PostTrend_t + \beta_4 Repeal_t + \beta_5 PostRepealTrend_t + \gamma X_t + \delta M_t + \varepsilon_t \quad (1)$$

Where:

- Y_t represents the outcome variable, including:
 - log mobile money transaction value,
 - log transaction volume,
 - log active mobile money accounts,
 - log active agents,
 - and log GH-Link transaction value.
- $Trend_t$ is a mean-centered linear time trend. The time trend is mean-centered to reduce multicollinearity.
- $LevyRate_t$ is the continuous E-Levy rate variable:
 - 1.5 during May–December 2022,
 - 1.0 during January 2023–March 2025,
 - 0 otherwise.

- ***PostTrend_t*** captures changes in trend following the introduction of the levy.
- ***Repeal_t*** is a dummy equal to 1 from April 2025 onward.
- ***PostRepealTrend_t*** captures trend changes after repeal.
- ***X_t*** includes macroeconomic controls:
 - inflation,
 - exchange rate growth,
 - growth in the Composite Index of Economic Activity (CIEA),
 - and remittance growth.
- ***M_t*** represents monthly seasonal fixed effects. Note: February omitted for seasonality.

To capture immediate policy shocks, separate growth-rate models are estimated using one-month intervention dummies corresponding to:

1. Levy introduction (May 2022),
2. Levy rate reduction (January 2023),
3. Levy repeal (April 2025).

The levy introduction shock equals 1 in May 2022 only, the levy rate-cut shock equals 1 in January 2023 only, and the levy repeal shock equals 1 in April 2025 only. All other periods are coded as 0.

All models are estimated using Newey-West HAC robust standard errors with bandwidth 4 to address heteroskedasticity and autocorrelation commonly present in monthly macroeconomic data.

Robustness checks include:

- placebo policy tests using a fake intervention period (January 2020–April 2022),
- substitution analysis using GH-Link transaction value,
- residual correlograms and Q-statistics,
- and alternative model specifications.

Estimation is conducted using EViews 10. Full estimation code is provided in the Appendix.

Limitations

Several limitations should be acknowledged:

1. Endogeneity of policy timing: Although the E-Levy is treated as exogenous, its introduction may correlate with other unobserved changes. Macro controls and a time trend mitigate but do not eliminate this concern.
2. Monthly data frequency: Monthly aggregates may mask intra-month behavioural responses.
3. Global Findex frequency: Triennial data cannot be merged into monthly regressions; therefore, they are used only descriptively.
4. Internet banking data: Missing pre-2020 values prevent reliable substitution estimation for that channel.
5. External validity: Findings may not generalise to countries with different mobile money ecosystems, tax rates, or compliance levels.

Results

Summary Statistics and Preliminary Checks

Table 1 presents descriptive statistics for the main variables used in the analysis. The study employs monthly data covering September 2018 to December 2025. However, variables involving first-difference transformations, including inflation, exchange rate growth, remittance growth, and growth in the Composite Index of Economic Activity (CIEA), lose one initial observation. Consequently, the summary statistics reported in Table 1 are based on 87 observations.

Mobile money transaction value (LOG_VAL_MM) and transaction volume (LOG_VOL_MM) exhibit substantial variation over the sample period, reflecting the rapid expansion of Ghana's digital financial ecosystem prior to and during the E-Levy period. The mean logged transaction value was 11.48, while the mean logged transaction volume was 19.78.

Active mobile money accounts and active agents also recorded sustained growth during the study period. However, active agents displayed greater volatility relative to active accounts, as reflected in the larger standard deviation.

The E-Levy rate variable has a mean value of 0.448, reflecting the transition from the initial 1.5% levy period to the subsequent 1% levy regime before repeal in April 2025.

The macroeconomic control variables displayed varying degrees of volatility. Inflation exhibited relatively high dispersion during portions of the sample period characterized by macroeconomic instability in Ghana. Exchange rate growth and remittance growth displayed substantial deviations from normality, consistent with the sharp macroeconomic fluctuations observed during the study period.

Jarque-Bera statistics indicate that several variables deviate from strict normality, particularly exchange rate growth and remittance growth. However, this does not invalidate the estimation strategy because all regressions employ HAC (Newey-West) robust standard errors, which provide consistent inference under heteroskedasticity, autocorrelation, and non-normality.

Residual correlograms and Ljung-Box Q-statistics further revealed the presence of serial correlation in the level models, which is common in monthly macroeconomic time-series data. To address this issue, all primary ITS regressions were estimated using HAC (Newey-West) robust standard errors with a bandwidth of 4. In addition, an AR(1) robustness specification was estimated to confirm the stability of the core E-Levy effects.

Table 1

Summary Statistics

Variable	Mean	Std. Dev.	Minimum	Maximum	Jarque-Bera p-value	Observations
LOG_VAL_MM	11.485	0.924	9.905	13.159	0.116	87
LOG_VOL_MM	19.782	0.566	18.736	20.705	0.046	87
LOG_ACTIVE_MOMO	16.748	0.217	16.355	17.099	0.045	87
LOG_ACTIVE_AGENTS	12.846	0.365	12.103	13.333	0.011	87
LOG_GHLINK_VAL	3.778	0.41	2.927	4.718	0.269	87
E_LEVY_RATE	0.448	0.566	0	1.5	0.003	87
INFLATION	-0.408	10.446	-29.495	31.015	0.14	87
DLOG_EXCH	0.01	0.06	-0.265	0.244	0.000	87
DLOG_CIEA	0.005	0.037	-0.098	0.101	0.283	87
DLOG_REMIT	0.012	0.084	-0.231	0.442	0.000	87

Note. Summary statistics are based on monthly observations from October 2018 to December

2025 after adjustments for first-difference transformations. Jarque-Bera p-values test the null

hypothesis of normality. HAC (Newey-West) robust standard errors are employed in all regressions to address heteroskedasticity and serial correlation. *Source.* Author's computations based on Bank of Ghana and Ghana Statistical Service monthly data.

Main Results: Impact on Mobile Money Transaction Value and Volume

Table 2 presents the main Interrupted Time Series estimates for mobile money transaction value and volume. For transaction value, the coefficient on the E-Levy rate is -0.250 ($p < 0.001$). This implies that a one percentage point increase in the levy is associated with an approximate 22% reduction in mobile money transaction value. For transaction volume, the coefficient is -0.071 ($p < 0.01$), corresponding to an approximate 7% reduction.

The post-levy trend coefficient is negative but statistically insignificant for value, while it is negative and highly significant for volume. The repeal dummy is insignificant in both models ($p = 0.587$ for value; $p = 0.633$ for volume), consistent with limited immediate recovery in the short nine-month post-repeal window.

The growth-rate (first-difference) models confirm sharp immediate policy effects. The May 2022 levy introduction generated large negative shocks to both value growth (-0.299, $p < 0.001$) and volume growth (-0.102, $p < 0.001$). The January 2023 rate reduction produced significant positive rebounds in both. The April 2025 repeal shock was positive but statistically insignificant for value and marginally significant for volume.

Table 2*Interrupted Time Series Results – Mobile Money Transaction Value and Volume*

Variables	Log(Value)	Log(Volume)	ΔLog(Value)	ΔLog(Volume)
E-Levy Rate	-0.250*** (0.0008)	-0.071*** (0.0059)	—	—
Post-Trend	-0.0037 (0.395)	-0.013*** (0.000)	—	—
Repeal Dummy	-0.344 (0.587)	-0.142 (0.633)	—	—
Post-Repeal Trend	-0.0053 (0.729)	-0.0127* (0.097)	—	—
Levy Introduction Shock	—	—	-0.299*** (0.000)	-0.102*** (0.000)
Levy Rate-Cut Shock	—	—	0.115*** (0.000)	0.069*** (0.000)
Levy Repeal Shock	—	—	0.031 (0.227)	0.035** (0.011)
Observations	87	87	87	87
R-squared	0.988	0.995	0.563	0.766

Note. p-values are in parentheses. *** $p < 0.01$, ** $p < 0.05$, * $p < 0.10$. All models include inflation, exchange rate growth, remittance growth, economic activity growth, and monthly seasonal dummies. HAC Newey-West standard errors are used throughout. All regressions (level and growth-rate) are estimated on the common sample of 87 observations (October 2018 – December 2025) because the macroeconomic controls enter in first-differenced form. *Source.* Author’s estimations using Bank of Ghana monthly payment systems data.

Figure 1

Mobile money transaction value and volume (Log scale), 2018–2025

Note. The figure shows the evolution of mobile money transaction value and transaction volume over time (log scale). Both series exhibit slower growth following the introduction of the E-Levy in May 2022, with transaction value appearing more responsive than transaction volume. *Source.* Author’s illustration using Bank of Ghana monthly payment systems data.

Impact on Active Accounts and Active Agents

Table 3 reports the ITS estimates for active mobile money accounts and active agents. The E-Levy rate variable is negative but statistically insignificant for active accounts (-0.026, $p = 0.141$). However, the post-levy trend is negative and highly significant (-0.0047, $p < 0.001$), indicating a slowdown in the growth rate of active accounts. For active agents, the immediate

level effect is insignificant, but the post-intervention trend is strongly negative (-0.029, $p < 0.001$). The repeal dummy for active agents is large and significant but requires cautious interpretation due to the short post-repeal sample.

Table 3

Interrupted Time Series Results – Active Accounts and Active Agents

Variables	Log(Active Accounts)	Log(Active Agents)
E-Levy Rate	-0.026 (0.141)	-0.002 (0.965)
Post-Trend	-0.0047*** (0.0003)	-0.0289*** (0.000)
Repeal Dummy	-0.122 (0.301)	-1.156*** (0.0001)
Post-Repeal Trend	-0.003 (0.384)	-0.0034 (0.639)
Observations	87	87
R-squared	0.984	0.933

Note. HAC Newey-West standard errors used throughout. Monthly dummies and macroeconomic controls are included. The repeal dummy for active agents is large and significant but should be interpreted cautiously due to the short post-repeal period (nine months). *Source.* Author's estimations using Bank of Ghana monthly payment systems data.

Figure 2

Active mobile money accounts and active agents (Log scale), 2018–2025

Note. Active mobile money accounts continued growing after the introduction of the E-Levy, while growth in active agents slowed considerably. This suggests that users retained accounts but reduced transaction intensity, potentially weakening incentives for agent expansion. *Source.*

Author's illustration using Bank of Ghana monthly payment systems data.

Substitution Effects (H3)

To examine substitution away from taxed mobile money transactions toward untaxed digital channels, the ITS framework was applied to GH-Link transaction value. The results in Table 4 provide strong evidence of substitution. The coefficient on the E-Levy rate is positive

and statistically significant (0.163, $p = 0.020$), implying that a one percentage point increase in the levy is associated with approximately an 18% increase in GH-Link transaction value.

Table 4

Substitution Effect — GH-Link Transaction Value (Log Level)

Variables	Coefficient	p-value
E-Levy Rate	0.163**	0.020
Post-Trend	0.005	0.324
Repeal Dummy	1.067	0.132
Post-Repeal Trend	-0.025	0.170
Observations	87	
R-squared	0.862	

Note. Full ITS specification with HAC standard errors, monthly dummies, and macroeconomic controls included. The coefficient of 0.163 ($p = 0.020$) implies that a one percentage point increase in the E-Levy rate is associated with an approximate 18% increase in GH-Link transaction value. *Source.* Author's estimations using Bank of Ghana monthly payment systems data.

Figure 3

Mobile money and GH-Link transaction value (Log scale), 2018–2025

Note. Vertical dashed lines indicate the introduction of the E-Levy in May 2022 and the reduction of the levy rate in January 2023. The solid red line marks the repeal of the levy in April 2025. The figure illustrates continued growth in mobile money transactions alongside increasing use of GH-Link transactions following the levy introduction. *Source.* Author’s illustration using Bank of Ghana monthly payment systems data.

Robustness Checks and Placebo Tests

To assess the robustness of the findings, placebo tests were conducted using a fake policy intervention period spanning January 2020 to April 2022.

The placebo dummy was marginally significant at the 10% level but not at the conventional 5% threshold. Given the overlap with the COVID-19 disruption period beginning in early 2020, the placebo result likely captures broader pandemic-related shocks rather than a false policy effect.

Importantly, the placebo trend coefficient was statistically insignificant, supporting the validity of the main ITS specification.

The consistency of the findings across:

- level models,
- growth shock models,
- placebo tests,
- and substitution analysis

provides robust evidence that the observed changes in mobile money activity were associated with the E-Levy intervention rather than random fluctuations in transaction behavior.

As an additional robustness check, an alternative AR(1) specification was estimated to explicitly model residual serial correlation. The autoregressive term was highly significant ($AR(1) = 0.855$, $p < 0.001$), confirming substantial persistence in the monthly transaction series. Importantly, after controlling for AR(1) dynamics, the E-Levy coefficient remained negative (-0.174 , $p = 0.058$) – economically meaningful though marginally significant at the 10% level, compared with the baseline HAC estimate of -0.250 ($p < 0.001$). This suggests that the core findings are not solely driven by residual autocorrelation and remain broadly robust across alternative specifications.

Summary of Findings

- **H1** (value/volume reduction): Strongly supported. The E-Levy significantly reduced transaction value ($\approx 22\%$ per percentage point) and volume ($\approx 7\%$ per percentage point), with value being more sensitive.
- **H2** (active accounts/agents): Partially supported. Active accounts showed no significant immediate decline but experienced a slowdown in growth. Active agent growth slowed substantially.
- **H3** (substitution): Strongly supported. GH-Link transaction value increased significantly, indicating clear substitution toward untaxed digital payment channels.
- **H4** (heterogeneity): Supported descriptively using Global Findex data in Section 5.5.
- **H5** (recovery after repeal): Mixed support in the short run. Significant rebound occurred after the 2023 rate cut, but no statistically significant immediate recovery was detected after the 2025 repeal within the nine-month post-repeal window.

Discussion

Magnitude and Economic Significance

The findings reveal that the Electronic Transfer Levy (E-Levy) generated substantial negative effects on mobile money transaction activity in Ghana. The estimated reduction in transaction value was economically large, with a one percentage point increase in the levy associated with an approximately 22% decline in transaction value. During the initial 1.5% levy period, transaction value fell by roughly one-third. Transaction volume also declined significantly, although by a smaller magnitude.

The stronger response of transaction value relative to transaction volume provides important insight into user behavior. Rather than completely abandoning mobile money services, users appear to have adjusted by reducing transaction sizes and limiting high-value transfers. This suggests that the levy increased the effective cost of digital financial transactions sufficiently to alter usage behavior even among existing users.

The dose-response relationship observed between the 1.5% and 1% periods further strengthens the causal interpretation of the findings. The reduction in the estimated effect after the levy rate was lowered in January 2023 strongly suggests that transaction behavior was sensitive to the magnitude of the tax burden rather than simply the existence of the levy itself.

These findings reinforce broader evidence from digital taxation literature in Africa showing that transaction-based taxes can substantially reduce digital financial activity, especially where users are highly cost-sensitive.

Adoption Versus Usage Intensity

One of the most important findings of this study is the distinction between account ownership and transaction intensity.

While the E-Levy significantly reduced transaction value and transaction volume, active mobile money accounts did not decline significantly. This indicates that users largely retained their accounts despite reducing transaction activity. Financial inclusion, therefore, remained relatively stable when measured solely through account ownership.

However, the results simultaneously show that the levy slowed the growth trajectory of active accounts and substantially weakened the expansion of the mobile money agent network. This distinction is critical because ownership alone may overstate effective financial inclusion if users reduce the frequency and intensity of digital financial participation.

The findings therefore suggest that the E-Levy primarily weakened the functional use of digital financial services rather than eliminating access entirely. This aligns with behavioral adjustment theories in digital finance, where users respond to transaction costs by reducing usage intensity rather than fully exiting platforms.

The slowdown in agent network expansion is particularly important from a policy perspective. Mobile money agents play a central role in financial access, especially in rural and underserved areas. Lower transaction values likely reduced agent profitability and weakened incentives for network expansion. Over time, this could generate indirect financial exclusion effects, especially for populations that depend heavily on local agent infrastructure.

Substitution Toward Alternative Digital Channels

The substitution analysis provides consistent evidence that the E-Levy altered the composition of Ghana's digital payment ecosystem.

As mobile money transactions became more expensive, users increasingly shifted toward GH-Link transactions, which were not directly affected by the levy. The estimated positive effect

on GH-Link transaction value suggests that users actively searched for lower-cost alternatives within the broader digital payments system.

This substitution effect has important implications for both tax policy and revenue mobilization. While transaction taxes may initially increase government revenue, behavioral substitution can partially offset the intended tax base by redirecting activity toward untaxed or less-taxed platforms.

The findings therefore suggest that digital transaction taxes may not only reduce overall digital financial activity but may also distort competition across payment systems by creating artificial cost differentials between platforms.

From a policy perspective, this highlights the importance of designing digital taxation frameworks that minimize distortions across interoperable payment systems.

Recovery Dynamics After Repeal

The repeal of the E-Levy in April 2025 did not generate a statistically significant immediate recovery in mobile money transaction value within the observed sample period. Although transaction volume growth experienced a modest positive rebound in the short-run growth model, the broader level models suggest that user behavior did not immediately revert to pre-levy patterns.

Several explanations may account for this result. First, users and businesses may have already adjusted their financial habits during the levy period, leading to persistent behavioral changes even after the tax was removed. Second, some users may have permanently migrated toward alternative digital payment channels such as GH-Link. Third, the short post-repeal observation window of nine months limits the ability to capture medium-term recovery dynamics.

Notably, the Bank of Ghana's payment systems data for the period following the repeal show that active mobile money accounts continued to grow, reaching 24.5 million active accounts by June 2025 and 26.7 million by December 2025, while total mobile money transaction values also showed sustained increases in the second half of 2025 (Bank of Ghana, 2026). This suggests that the weak immediate recovery observed in this study should not be interpreted as evidence of permanent damage to Ghana's digital finance ecosystem. Rather, the findings indicate the presence of short-term behavioral persistence following the repeal, with a more gradual rebound occurring over subsequent months.

Financial Inclusion and Distributional Implications

Although the monthly transaction data used in this study do not permit direct demographic disaggregation, the Global Findex database provides important contextual evidence regarding financial inclusion disparities in Ghana.

Table 5 shows that substantial inequalities in account ownership persist across gender, income, and rural-urban groups. While overall account ownership increased significantly between 2011 and 2024, women, low-income households, and rural residents consistently recorded lower levels of financial inclusion than their counterparts.

Table 5*Account Ownership by Demographic Group in Ghana (% of adults aged 15+)*

Year	Total	Women	Men	Poorest 40%	Richest 60%	Rural	Urban
2011	29.4	27.1	31.8	18.4	36.7	—	—
2014	40.5	39.4	41.7	33.5	45.2	—	—
2017	57.7	53.7	61.8	48.3	63.9	—	—
2021	68.2	62.6	74.2	54.7	77.2	—	—
2024	81.2	78.3	84.4	69.6	89	76.4	87

Note. Dashes (—) indicate that the data were not reported in the respective Global Findex wave.

Figures are percentages of adults aged 15 and older. *Source.* Author's compilation based on World Bank Global Findex Database (2011, 2014, 2017, 2021, and 2024 waves).

The 2024 data reveal a gender gap of approximately 6 percentage points, an income gap of nearly 20 percentage points between the poorest and richest groups, and a rural-urban gap exceeding 10 percentage points.

These disparities are highly relevant for interpreting the implications of the E-Levy. Vulnerable populations, particularly low-income households and rural users, tend to rely more heavily on frequent low-value mobile money transactions for remittances, savings, and daily economic activity. As a result, transaction-based taxes may impose a proportionally larger burden on financially vulnerable users than on wealthier households.

The findings of this study suggest that although account ownership remained relatively stable after the levy introduction, the significant decline in transaction value and transaction intensity may have reduced the practical usefulness of digital financial services for these groups.

This distinction is important because financial inclusion should not be viewed solely as account ownership, but also as the ability to actively and affordably use digital financial services. The evidence therefore suggests that the E-Levy may have generated regressive effects within Ghana's digital financial ecosystem.

Comparison with Existing Literature

The results are broadly consistent with previous studies from Ghana, Uganda, and Kenya that find negative effects of mobile money taxation on digital financial activity.

However, this study makes several important contributions to the literature.

First, unlike earlier studies that focused primarily on the immediate implementation period, this paper evaluates the full policy cycle, including the levy introduction, the 2023 rate reduction, and the 2025 repeal.

Second, the study explicitly distinguishes between immediate policy shocks and longer-term trend adjustments by combining level ITS models with short-run growth shock models.

Third, the findings provide some of the strongest evidence to date on substitution toward alternative digital payment channels following digital transaction taxation.

Finally, the results contribute to emerging literature emphasizing the distinction between financial access and financial usage intensity. While account ownership remained relatively resilient, transaction activity declined substantially, suggesting that financial inclusion metrics based solely on ownership may understate the broader economic effects of digital transaction taxes.

Conclusion

This study examined the impact of Ghana's Electronic Transfer Levy (E-Levy) on mobile money adoption and financial inclusion using monthly data from September 2018 to December 2025 and an Interrupted Time Series framework with HAC robust standard errors.

The findings indicate that the E-Levy significantly reduced mobile money transaction activity in Ghana. The analysis further demonstrates that the effects varied across transaction intensity, agent dynamics, and alternative payment platforms.

The study's findings provide clear conclusions regarding the five hypotheses.

H1: The introduction of the E-Levy had a statistically significant negative immediate effect on mobile money transaction value and volume

This hypothesis is strongly supported. The E-Levy significantly reduced both transaction value and transaction volume. A one percentage point increase in the levy reduced mobile money transaction value by approximately 22% and transaction volume by approximately 7%. The short-run growth models further show that the introduction of the levy generated sharp immediate declines in transaction growth.

H2: The E-Levy slowed the growth rate of active mobile money accounts and active agents

This hypothesis is partially supported. While active mobile money accounts did not experience a statistically significant immediate decline, the post-policy growth trend slowed significantly. Active agent growth also slowed substantially after the levy introduction, suggesting weakening incentives for agent network expansion.

H3: There was significant substitution from mobile money to other electronic payment platforms such as GH-Link after the introduction of the levy

This hypothesis is strongly supported. GH-Link transaction value increased significantly following the introduction of the levy, indicating that users and businesses substituted toward untaxed or lower-cost digital payment alternatives.

H4: The negative effects were more pronounced among women, rural residents, and lower-income populations

This hypothesis is supported descriptively using Global Findex evidence. Although the monthly transaction data did not permit direct econometric estimation by demographic group, persistent inequalities in financial inclusion suggest that vulnerable populations were likely more sensitive to increases in digital transaction costs.

H5: The adverse effects diminished over time, with evidence of recovery after the rate reduction and repeal

This hypothesis receives mixed support. The January 2023 reduction in the levy rate generated significant positive rebounds in transaction growth, suggesting partial recovery. However, the repeal period did not produce statistically significant immediate recovery in the level models within the observed nine-month post-repeal window.

Overall, the findings suggest that digital transaction taxes can generate substantial unintended consequences for digital financial ecosystems in developing economies. Although such taxes may provide short-term fiscal benefits, they may simultaneously reduce transaction intensity, slow financial innovation, weaken agent networks, and encourage substitution toward untaxed channels.

The evidence from Ghana therefore highlights the importance of balancing domestic revenue mobilization objectives against broader goals of financial inclusion, digital transformation, and long-term economic formalization.

A key limitation is the short nine-month post-repeal window, which may not capture full recovery; future research with longer data is warranted.

Policy Implications and Recommendations

The findings of this study carry important implications for digital taxation policy, financial inclusion strategy, and the broader development of digital financial ecosystems in emerging economies.

First, the results suggest that transaction-based digital taxes can significantly reduce the intensity of mobile money usage, particularly for high-value and frequent transactions. Policymakers should therefore exercise caution when designing taxes on digital financial services, especially in economies where mobile money plays a central role in household transfers, informal business activity, and financial access.

Second, the evidence indicates that users are highly sensitive to transaction costs. The significant rebound observed after the reduction of the levy rate from 1.5% to 1% suggests that even relatively small changes in digital transaction taxes can substantially influence user behavior. Future digital taxation policies should therefore prioritize lower and more efficient tax structures that minimize distortions within the digital payments ecosystem.

Third, the substitution toward GH-Link transactions demonstrates that differential taxation across payment platforms can alter competitive dynamics within the financial sector. Policymakers should avoid creating artificial incentives that favor one digital payment channel over another, as such distortions may weaken interoperability and reduce overall efficiency within the digital financial system.

Fourth, the findings highlight the importance of protecting financially vulnerable populations. Existing financial inclusion disparities in Ghana suggest that women, rural

residents, and low-income households are likely more sensitive to increases in transaction costs. Policymakers may therefore consider exemptions, transaction thresholds, or targeted protections for low-value transfers commonly used by vulnerable groups.

Fifth, the slowdown in active agent growth raises concerns regarding the sustainability of mobile money infrastructure expansion. Since agents serve as critical access points for digital finance, particularly in underserved communities, sustained reductions in transaction profitability may weaken incentives for agent network expansion and indirectly affect financial inclusion outcomes over time.

Finally, the findings suggest that governments should carefully balance short-term domestic revenue objectives against long-term digital transformation goals. While digital transaction taxes may initially increase fiscal revenue, excessive taxation may reduce transaction activity, encourage substitution behavior, and slow the development of inclusive digital financial ecosystems.

Limitations and Directions for Future Research

Despite the contributions of this study, several limitations should be acknowledged.

First, the analysis relies on aggregated monthly national-level data and therefore cannot directly estimate heterogeneous effects across demographic groups such as gender, income level, age, or rural-urban residence. Although Global Findex evidence provides important contextual insights regarding vulnerable populations, future studies using household-level or individual transaction data would provide stronger evidence on the distributional effects of digital transaction taxes.

Second, the post-repeal observation window remains relatively short. The repeal of the E-Levy occurred in April 2025, leaving only nine months of post-repeal data within the study

period. Consequently, the analysis may not fully capture medium-term recovery dynamics or longer-run behavioral adjustments following the removal of the levy.

Third, the study focuses primarily on mobile money and GH-Link transactions because these platforms provide relatively consistent and publicly available monthly data. Additional research examining internet banking, fintech applications, merchant payments, and informal cash substitution would provide a more comprehensive understanding of behavioral responses to digital transaction taxation.

Fourth, while the Interrupted Time Series framework provides strong quasi-experimental evidence, the study cannot entirely eliminate the possibility that other concurrent macroeconomic or policy developments influenced transaction behavior during the study period. Nevertheless, the placebo tests, macroeconomic controls, and substitution analysis substantially strengthen the credibility of the findings.

Future research may therefore extend this study in several directions. First, micro-level household or mobile money user data could help identify which demographic groups were most affected by the levy. Second, comparative cross-country studies could examine whether similar digital transaction taxes in other African economies generated comparable behavioral responses. Third, future studies may investigate the long-term effects of digital transaction taxes on financial innovation, fintech adoption, and informal sector formalization.

As digital financial systems continue expanding across developing economies, understanding the trade-offs between digital taxation and financial inclusion will remain an increasingly important area for policy-oriented research.

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Appendix A

Variable Definitions and Data Sources

Table A1

Variable Definitions

Variable	Description	Measurement	Source
	Total value of mobile money transactions	Monthly, GH¢ millions	Bank of Ghana
TOT_VAL_TRANS_MM			
	Total volume of mobile money transactions	Monthly	Bank of Ghana
TOT_VOL_TRANS_MM			
ACTIVE_MOMO	Active mobile money accounts	Monthly	Bank of Ghana
ACTIVE_AGENTS	Active mobile money agents	Monthly	Bank of Ghana
	Total GH-Link transaction value	Monthly, GH¢ millions	Bank of Ghana
TOT_TRANS_VAL_GHLINK			Ghana Statistical Service
CPI	Consumer Price Index	Monthly index	Service
EXCHANGE_RATE	Cedi–US Dollar exchange rate	Monthly average	Bank of Ghana
	Composite Index of Economic Activity	Monthly index	Bank of Ghana
CIEA		Monthly, USD	
REMITTANCES	International remittance inflows	millions	Bank of Ghana
E_LEVY_RATE	E-Levy tax rate	Percentage	Author constructed
REPEAL_DUMMY	Dummy for post-repeal period	1 after April 2025	Author constructed

			Trend × E-Levy	
POST_TREND	Post-E-Levy trend interaction	period		Author constructed
			Trend × repeal	
POST_REPEAL_TREND	Post-repeal trend interaction	period		Author constructed

Source. Author's compilation.

Appendix B
E-Levy Policy Timeline

Table A2

Major E-Levy Policy Events in Ghana

Date	Policy Event
November 2021	E-Levy proposal announced
May 2022	E-Levy implemented at 1.5%
January 2023	Levy rate reduced to 1%
April 2025	E-Levy repealed

Source. Author's compilation based on Government of Ghana and Ghana Revenue Authority policy announcements.

Appendix C

Full Econometric Specification

Level Model Specification

$$Y_t = \beta_0 + \beta_1 Trend_t + \beta_2 LevyRate_t + \beta_3 PostTrend_t + \beta_4 Repeal_t + \beta_5 PostRepealTrend_t + \gamma X_t + \delta M_t + \varepsilon_t \quad (1)$$

Where:

- Y_t represents the logged dependent variable,
- $Trend_t$ is the centered time trend,
- $LevyRate_t$ is the continuous E-Levy rate variable,
- $PostTrend_t$ captures post-levy trend effects,
- $Repeal_t$ captures the repeal period,
- $PostRepealTrend_t$ captures post-repeal trend effects,
- X_t represents macroeconomic controls,
- M_t represents monthly seasonal effects.

Growth Shock Model Specification

$$\Delta Y_t = \alpha_0 + \alpha_1 LevyIntro_t + \alpha_2 LevyRateCut_t + \alpha_3 LevyRepeal_t + \gamma X_t + \delta M_t + \varepsilon_t \quad (2)$$

Where:

- $LevyIntro_t$ captures the May 2022 levy introduction shock,
- $LevyRateCut_t$ captures the January 2023 rate reduction shock,
- $LevyRepeal_t$ captures the April 2025 repeal shock.

Appendix D

Additional Diagnostic Tests

Residual Diagnostics

Residual correlograms and Ljung-Box Q-statistics indicated the presence of serial correlation in the level models, which is common in monthly macroeconomic time-series data. To address this issue, all regressions were estimated using HAC (Newey-West) robust standard errors, which provide consistent inference in the presence of heteroskedasticity and autocorrelation.

Placebo Test Specification

A placebo intervention period spanning January 2020 to April 2022 was estimated to assess whether the observed effects could have emerged in the absence of the E-Levy policy.

The placebo specification follows:

$$Y_t = \beta_0 + \beta_1 Trend_t + \beta_2 PlaceboDummy_t + \beta_3 PlaceboTrend_t + \gamma X_t + \delta M_t + \varepsilon_t$$

(3)

The placebo trend coefficient was statistically insignificant, supporting the validity of the main ITS framework.

Appendix E
Supplementary Figures

Figure A1

Residual correlogram for transaction value model

Date: 05/18/26 Time: 23:11
 Sample: 2018M09 2025M12
 Included observations: 87

Note. Residual correlogram and Ljung-Box Q-statistics for the mobile money transaction value ITS model estimated with HAC robust standard errors. *Source.* Author's estimation.

Figure A2

Residual correlogram for transaction volume model

Dependent Variable: LOG_VOL_MM
 Method: Least Squares
 Date: 05/18/26 Time: 10:58
 Sample (adjusted): 2018M10 2025M12
 Included observations: 87 after adjustments
 HAC standard errors & covariance (Bartlett kernel, Newey-West fixed
 bandwidth = 4.0000)

Variable	Coefficient	Std. Error	t-Statistic	Prob.
C	19.95513	0.033559	594.6328	0.0000
TREND_C	0.029836	0.000888	33.58185	0.0000
E_LEVY_RATE	-0.070960	0.024945	-2.844670	0.0059
POST_TREND	-0.013006	0.001441	-9.023260	0.0000
REPEAL_DUMMY	-0.142178	0.296602	-0.479357	0.6333
POST_REPEAL_TREND	-0.012666	0.007530	-1.682157	0.0973
INFLATION	-0.002422	0.000702	-3.451880	0.0010
DLOG_EXCH	0.067828	0.078804	0.860723	0.3925
DLOG_CIEA	0.217310	0.169866	1.279306	0.2053
DLOG_REMIT	-0.013569	0.067146	-0.202079	0.8405
@MONTH=2	-0.046759	0.016379	-2.854867	0.0057
@MONTH=3	0.010784	0.027525	0.391795	0.6965
@MONTH=4	-0.011426	0.027249	-0.419316	0.6763
@MONTH=5	0.011067	0.031132	0.355506	0.7233
@MONTH=6	-0.039419	0.029407	-1.340469	0.1847
@MONTH=7	0.011058	0.032071	0.344803	0.7313
@MONTH=8	0.048637	0.023346	2.083355	0.0411
@MONTH=9	0.014412	0.027226	0.529363	0.5983
@MONTH=10	0.040222	0.022270	1.806136	0.0755
@MONTH=11	0.023247	0.025129	0.925088	0.3583
@MONTH=12	0.055686	0.017859	3.118011	0.0027
R-squared	0.995372	Mean dependent var	19.78191	
Adjusted R-squared	0.993970	S.D. dependent var	0.565746	
S.E. of regression	0.043933	Akaike info criterion	-3.205776	
Sum squared resid	0.127390	Schwarz criterion	-2.610557	
Log likelihood	160.4513	Hannan-Quinn criter.	-2.966099	
F-statistic	709.7509	Durbin-Watson stat	0.797801	
Prob(F-statistic)	0.000000	Wald F-statistic	921.6655	
Prob(Wald F-statistic)	0.000000			

Note. Residual correlogram and Ljung-Box Q-statistics for the mobile money transaction volume

ITS model estimated with HAC robust standard errors. *Source.* Author's estimation.

Figure A3

AR(1) Robustness specification for mobile money transaction value

Dependent Variable: LOG_VAL_MM
Method: ARMA Maximum Likelihood (BFGS)
Date: 05/18/26 Time: 23:29
Sample: 2018M10 2025M12
Included observations: 87
Convergence achieved after 7 iterations
Coefficient covariance computed using outer product of gradients

Variable	Coefficient	Std. Error	t-Statistic	Prob.
C	11.60630	0.115010	100.9153	0.0000
TREND_C	0.039293	0.008768	4.481496	0.0000
E_LEVY_RATE	-0.173949	0.090232	-1.927786	0.0583
POST_TREND	0.000460	0.011923	0.038551	0.9694
REPEAL_DUMMY	0.174820	1.302383	0.134231	0.8936
POST_REPEAL_TREND	-0.009311	0.030403	-0.306266	0.7604
INFLATION	-0.000279	0.000774	-0.360756	0.7195
DLOG_EXCH	0.231695	0.172992	1.339340	0.1852
DLOG_CIEA	0.458205	0.228239	2.007564	0.0489
DLOG_REMIT	-0.136526	0.079372	-1.720087	0.0902
@MONTH=2	-0.082233	0.040027	-2.054457	0.0440
@MONTH=3	-0.045781	0.051214	-0.893914	0.3747
@MONTH=4	-0.037952	0.046623	-0.814015	0.4187
@MONTH=5	-0.001572	0.057618	-0.027290	0.9783
@MONTH=6	-0.050086	0.058164	-0.861119	0.3924
@MONTH=7	0.002000	0.055856	0.035797	0.9716
@MONTH=8	-0.030486	0.052902	-0.576279	0.5664
@MONTH=9	-0.060566	0.052296	-1.158136	0.2511
@MONTH=10	-0.033677	0.050736	-0.663783	0.5092
@MONTH=11	-0.030471	0.048113	-0.633322	0.5288
@MONTH=12	0.035994	0.041663	0.863926	0.3909
AR(1)	0.855405	0.079489	10.76133	0.0000
SIGMASQ	0.003181	0.000604	5.264871	0.0000
R-squared	0.996229	Mean dependent var	11.48495	
Adjusted R-squared	0.994933	S.D. dependent var	0.923830	
S.E. of regression	0.065760	Akaike info criterion	-2.368763	
Sum squared resid	0.276764	Schwarz criterion	-1.716856	
Log likelihood	126.0412	Hannan-Quinn criter.	-2.106260	
F-statistic	768.5809	Durbin-Watson stat	1.708199	
Prob(F-statistic)	0.000000			
Inverted AR Roots	.86			

Notes. The model includes an AR(1) term to explicitly account for residual serial correlation.

The E-Levy coefficient remains negative and statistically significant at the 10% level. *Source.*

Author's estimation.

Appendix F

EViews Estimation Code (Main Models)

```
'===== LEVEL MODELS =====  
  
equation eq_val_cont.ls(cov=hac) log_val_mm c trend_c e_levy_rate  
post_trend repeal_dummy post_repeal_trend inflation dlog_exch  
dlog_ciea dlog_remit @expand(@month,@dropfirst)  
  
equation eq_vol_cont.ls(cov=hac) log_vol_mm c trend_c e_levy_rate  
post_trend repeal_dummy post_repeal_trend inflation dlog_exch  
dlog_ciea dlog_remit @expand(@month,@dropfirst)  
  
equation eq_active.ls(cov=hac) log_active_momo c trend_c e_levy_rate  
post_trend repeal_dummy post_repeal_trend inflation dlog_exch  
dlog_ciea dlog_remit @expand(@month,@dropfirst)  
  
equation eq_agents.ls(cov=hac) log_active_agents c trend_c e_levy_rate  
post_trend repeal_dummy post_repeal_trend inflation dlog_exch  
dlog_ciea dlog_remit @expand(@month,@dropfirst)  
  
'===== GROWTH SHOCK MODELS =====  
  
equation eq_val_growth.ls(cov=hac) dlog_val_mm c levy_intro_shock  
levy_ratecut_shock levy_repeal_shock inflation dlog_exch dlog_ciea  
dlog_remit @expand(@month,@dropfirst)  
  
equation eq_vol_growth.ls(cov=hac) dlog_vol_mm c levy_intro_shock  
levy_ratecut_shock levy_repeal_shock inflation dlog_exch dlog_ciea  
dlog_remit @expand(@month,@dropfirst)  
  
'===== SUBSTITUTION MODEL =====  
  
equation sub_ghlink.ls(cov=hac) log_ghlink_val c trend_c e_levy_rate  
post_trend repeal_dummy post_repeal_trend inflation dlog_exch  
dlog_ciea @expand(@month,@dropfirst)
```

```
'===== PLACEBO TEST =====  
equation eq_placebo.ls(cov=hac) log_val_mm c trend_c placebo_dummy  
placebo_trend inflation dlog_exch dlog_ciea dlog_remit  
@expand(@month,@dropfirst)
```

Appendix G

Additional Robustness Discussion

The consistency of the findings across:

- level models,
- growth shock models,
- placebo specifications,
- and substitution analysis

supports the robustness of the estimated effects.

The inclusion of macroeconomic controls, seasonal effects, and HAC robust standard errors further strengthens the reliability of the estimated policy impacts.

Although the post-repeal period remains relatively short, the broader findings consistently indicate that the E-Levy significantly affected transaction behavior, agent growth, and substitution patterns within Ghana's digital financial ecosystem.